

DTws Intantiation using WoTDT ontology

- DTw developer
- Domain expert

DTw developer

DTws

DTws metadata
extraction by
dimension

Metadata Intantiation
using WoTDT
ontology

DTws metadata
by dimension

DTws metadata
instantiation